

Correction

Correction: Marotta et al. Towards Positive Energy Districts: Energy Renovation of a Mediterranean District and Activation of Energy Flexibility. *Solar* 2023, 3, 253–282

Iliara Marotta ^{1,*}, Maurizio Cellura ¹
and Jaume Salom ²

¹ Department of Engineering, University of Palermo, Viale Delle Scienze, Building 9, 90128 Palermo, Italy

² Catalonia Institute for Energy Research (IREC), Jardins de les Dones de Negre 1, 08930 Barcelona, Spain

* Correspondence: iliana.marotta01@unipa.it

Following publication, the Editorial Office became aware that the original article [1] lacks a citation to the previously published Spanish conference paper [2].

Adhering to our standard procedure, the Editorial Office conducted an investigation with the support of the Editorial Board and in full collaboration with the authors. The evaluation confirmed the lack of citation for the previously published Spanish conference paper [2] which was found to be inconsistent with MDPI's citation policy, though it did not constitute redundancy. The authors agreed to correct the publication by achieving the following:

We update the article title note: † The present work is an extension of the “Hacia Distritos De Energía Positiva: Rediseño De Un Distrito Mediterráneo Mediante La Integración De Tecnologías Solares Y La Activación De La Flexibilidad Energética” presented to “XVIII Congreso Ibérico y XIV Congreso Iberoamericano de Energía Solar, Palma, Spain, 20–22 June 2022; pp. 45–53.”

We add the following information: “This is an extended version of the conference paper [48].”. This is added to Section 1.2., Objective and Structure of the Study, paragraph number 17, after the bullet points.

We add reference 48 [2] to the reference list. With this correction, the order of some references has been adjusted accordingly. The authors state that the scientific conclusions are unaffected. This correction was approved by the Academic Editor. The original publication has also been updated.

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References

1. Marotta, I.; Péan, T.; Guarino, F.; Longo, S.; Cellura, M.; Salom, J. Towards Positive Energy Districts: Energy Renovation of a Mediterranean District and Activation of Energy Flexibility. *Solar* 2023, 3, 253–282. [[CrossRef](#)]
2. Marotta, I.; Péan, T.; Tamm, M.; Guarino, F.; Longo, S.; Cellura, M.; Salom, J. Hacia Distritos De Energía Positiva: Rediseño De Un Distrito Mediterráneo Mediante La Integración De Tecnologías Solares Y La Activación De La Flexibilidad Energética. In Proceedings of the XVIII Congreso Ibérico y XIV Congreso Iberoamericano de Energía Solar, Palma, Spain, 20–22 June 2022; pp. 45–53.

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